

KOMPETENSI PROFESIONAL GURU GEOGRAFI DALAM PROSES PEMBELAJARAN MATERI LINGKUNGAN HIDUP DI KELAS XI SMA NEGERI 10 SINGKAWANG

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Abstrak

Tujuan penelitian adalah untuk mengembangkan pembelajaran geografi melalui kompetensi profesional guru geografi dalam proses pembelajaran materi Lingkungan Hidup di Kelas XI Sekolah Menengah Atas Negeri 10 Singkawang. Penelitian merupakan penelitian kuantitatif berjenis deskriptif dan asosiatif yaitu menggunakan APKG 1 dan 2 sebagai alat ukur. Dari hasil penelitian APKG 1 memperoleh nilai 3,65 dengan kategori sangat baik dan APKG 2 memperoleh nilai 3,35 dengan kategori sangat baik. Sedangkan dari hasil angket 75,52 dengan kategori sangat baik. Berdasarkan hasil penelitian diketahui bahwa kompetensi profesional guru geografi dapat mengembangkan proses pembelajaran materi Lingkungan Hidup kelas XI SMA Negeri 10 Singkawang dengan kategori sangat baik.

Kata Kunci: kompetensi profesional guru, proses pembelajaran, lingkungan hidup.

Abstract

The purpose of this study was to develop geography learning through the professional competence of geography teachers in the learning process of Environmental Materials at the eleventh grade students of SMAN 10 Singkawang. This research is a descriptive and associative quantitative research of APKG 1 and 2 as a measurement tool. The result of the research showed that: (1) APKG 1 score is 3.65 which was categorized as very good; (2) APKG 2 score is 3.35 which was categorized as very good; and (3) the finding also revealed that questionnaire score is 75.52 which was categorized as very good. As for the results of this study known that the professional competence of geography teachers can develop the learning process of environmental material on the eleventh grade students of SMAN 10 Singkawang which was categorized as very good.

Keywords: teacher profesional competence, learning process, environment.